

Digitalization has expanded to the point where it is an actor in every aspect of human life, and an important factor in our ability to maintain peace and democracy. If we identify and manage properly the challenges this poses, we stand to gain greatly.

The impact of technological evolution... on humans and societies

By THOMAS HOBERG

As information technology has transformed from a faster way to calculate numbers to the default way of professional and personal interaction, it has become mostly about content, where common ground for cultures, nations, religions and even couples can be much harder to find. What started as niche local products has become highly political, merely by scaling to billions of users, a natural threat to any leader who cannot control it, and to consumers who cannot escape it. Yet for sustained economic growth, we need to keep scaling it, without destroying its value or the planet.

Key insights

- The IT industry has reached the size of humanity and is exhausting its capacity for content consumption. Significant and sustainable growth could be created through products and services enabled for operation through smart virtual assistants, if their owners can trust them to remain loyal to them.
- The West believes opinions should spread freely, but technology be controlled; the East believes technology should be freely shared, but the spread of opinions needs tight control. As the majority of all human interaction becomes digital, cloud giants need to transform from private corporate ethics to comply with the huge diversity of ground rules.
- Content which self-optimizes for consumer consumption, naturally becomes more addictive, less objective and risks breaking established social code.
- Culture, traditions, beliefs and legal frameworks are the social code that keep societies working with minimal friction between humans. When humanity moves the majority of its interactions to the digital space, pieces of software used by the majority of users also become social code, simply because of the scale of its applications and the embedded decision making it contains. The governance used for the previous social code must then be extended to such software.
- We are in a new type of cold war, attempting destabilization and control over foreign nations via control over technology to achieve dominance, while the planet requires global collaboration.

Key recommendations

- Extending the value of a multitude of devices via computational intelligence without compromising their utility by increased individual need for attention, requires that the individual devices be holistically managed by no more than one virtual personal assistant per major domain.
- Support sustainable value of devices and virtual personal assistants via open standards, open source assets and regulation.
- Develop, support and mandate the use of modular and multiple compliance and ethics frameworks for code and content so distinct enclaves for e.g. owner, corporate, parent, vendor, government or party service provider can co-exist safely, without compromising owner sovereignty in the EU.
- Mandate the decoupling of corporate ethics from current web giant products and services within the EU and value system allies.

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The challenge of sustainable economic growth at planetary scale

A smartphone is one of the most complex industrial products that we have today, yet everybody who can obtain value from owning one, already has one. And most already spend as much time with the device or on a content platform as they can afford to. There is no incremental value in having twice or ten times as many phones, multiplying your social media channels or the time you spend with either—or their permutations; we are stuck at the scale of humanity.

And it's not that different for any other complex industrial product, be it a car, a climate control system or a washing machine: the potential demand no longer has orders of magnitude of growth remaining, and the actual demand is increasingly satisfied by producers outside of Europe.

To retain significant economic potential, Europe needs to overcome this barrier of human scale and find products or

services scaling several orders of magnitude beyond. These must still be valuable to human consumers to buy, but without placing undue strain on consumer budget or attention and without endangering Europe's stringent goals on sustainability and citizen benefits.

The vision of cyber-physical systems (CPS) or an internet of things (IoT) was created as one avenue to achieve this seemingly impossible mission, of providing economic growth far beyond human scale in the world of IT [1].

IoT for growth beyond human scale

The vision of IoT is to embed digital controls into products as we replace them, and to employ application program interfaces (APIs) to match them with services. We then design these services to increase the level of convenience, e.g. through autonomy, seamless integration or additional control, depending on personal preference. And for Europe we need to ensure that neither sustainability nor civil liberties

suffer, while our products are globally more competitive because of it.

Current approaches, whether they are called Siri, Alexa, Cortana, Google Assistant or WeChat fall seriously short, because they don't put these virtues up front. Yet they have created valuable concepts and open source assets, which Europe must quickly expand to build a powerhouse of product and service offerings. These offerings need to be sustainable not only environmentally, but also as a long term service offering to consumers, who can trust that their investment in adapting habits to match this mesh of assistants and devices will bring life-long benefits that will not simply disappear after a few months or years, as vendors merge or fail, and will not turn them into a victims of addiction, price-hikes or ransomware.

Europe is in a much better position to deliver sustainable user benefits than US or Chinese internet giants, whose culture and business models do not match. But as

both struggle to grow beyond their home territories, they will catch up quickly. We have a chance, but we need to make haste, because sustainable growth seems difficult to find elsewhere.

Scale vs. resilience in a world torn between globalization and isolationism

Because scale in IT is so important, it is naturally global, unless it's constrained artificially. Historically, some governments have tried to protect their local IT industry from competition via tariffs and import restrictions; likewise, there was a long history of export restrictions during the Cold War. But generally, the US IT industry has done rather well at using its Second World War-induced lead and huge domestic market to outpace competitors everywhere on the planet, as long as the competition was limited to technology.

With the rise of the internet and digitalization, IT also became about content, and content contains culture, beliefs, rules and values. These are areas where countries like China or Russia, Iran or Cuba obviously beg to differ: even Europe finds itself diverted and divided over the threat of a naked nipple vs. a concealed gun or free vs. hate speech.

China decided early on that the free flow of content and culture needed tight controls, while it found it harder to accept that the free exchange of technology or intellectual assets should be restricted. This East-West double barrier created a walled garden, which allowed China's domestic digital industry to flourish under careful government control to a scale where it stands to outgrow that of the United States—and with better future projections.

At this point, the United States is trying to turn the tide, leveraging every bit of control it has left, with Europe and most other nations on the planet stuck somewhere in the middle. The European Union was created with the vision of uniting its member states with their rather large diversity in culture, values and legislation into a single economy much bigger than any nation alone. Europe's clear choice was to take a running leap to expand this expe-

rience of managing diversity and modular regulation to the rest of the world: it had painfully learned not to impose religion or national ideology on neighbours and not to mistake isolationism for autonomy and thus risk insignificance.

Today we experience how long-standing international agreements are broken for national political expedience; we live in a world of constant cyberwarfare that can flare into physical trade wars, or worse, at any moment. Since Europe cannot control how the major nations swing between protectionism and free trade, it needs to operate with a strategy that works as well as possible with both, a multi-lateral open global market and deep trade and cyberwar trenches.

Within the domain of IT, digital and open source assets are more naturally global while physical and proprietary ones are more likely under the control of companies which can be coerced by governments. As a consequence, Europe must use, encourage, protect, produce and spread open source assets and avoid foreign proprietary ones to ensure sovereignty. And one of the most critical challenges here is making open source financially viable.

It should be noted that for the discussion of 'open source', we treat code and data as synonymous, not limited to computer source code, but including intellectual property assets, hardware description language code, datasets, recordings, images, video, books, designs, specifications, protocols, rule-sets, neural network training results etc.; in short, any digital content or binary encoded immaterial asset that is made available for copying and modification.

Europe needs to ensure that its citizens, its industries and its governments have complete access to all the cyber-physical systems components that they might need or want at prices and effort levels that are globally competitive.

The aspects of empowerment according to consumers, vendors and governments

Computers, and especially the 'very personal computers' somehow still called smartphones, have become a bit of everything: a tool to the point of a digital brain extension or an internet limb, and a digital serf, secretary or butler we can hardly do without.

They extend our senses and limbs, our mouth and individual reach from arm's length to around the globe and to everyone else likewise equipped; they give us telekinetic and telepathic powers over everything or everyone connected to the Internet. Their potential to empower provides a maximum of value to their owner, yet could put a nuclear launch button into the hands of a misguided kid, or grant titan mind changing powers to moral dwarfs: what consumers consider value, governments consider a potential threat while internet giants simply treat it as their own.

The original personal computer was regarded much like any other valuable tool or costly appliance at home or in the office: nobody but the owner could decide how and by whom it was used, and the attempt by a third party to access its data or use it without permission was considered hacking and a crime. The far more personal computers in our pockets currently receive a treatment that would have been classified as hacking thirty years ago, yet are claimed as a new normal by those with vested interests. GAF A and BATX have long sold devices and applications that might be considered foreign/antagonistic informers/denunciators and influencers/manipulators, when owners deserve undivided loyalty. And even democratic governments, who should be fighting such misuse, seem more interested in turning phones owned by citizens into agents of state and guardians of public health e.g. to fight the COVID-19 pandemic.

In this triangle of owners, vendors and governments, only the owner is the one who chooses to invest based on obtainable value, but the other two seem invested at reducing choice. Since devices and services that are disloyal to their owners

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and consumers attain little or even negative value to the one who pays, this trend chokes off value creation, before it can really take off.

Europe should neither prescribe how other geographies and value systems operate this most personal computing space, nor suffer foreign intervention: when relationships become digital, the law on the ground also needs to govern clouds above. Current early implementations of smart assistants like Amazon's Alexa or Apple's Siri tie corporate ethics and US regulation to technology and consumers to the device vendor: both are very much limiting their usefulness to the lowest common denominator internationally. If digital assistants are to become as smart and resourceful as a well-trained butler thirty years with the family, that would require a level of discretion and loyalty to their owners, which is impossible to sustain with current business and operating models.

Europe's unique opportunity here lies in the fact that it doesn't have an industry that depends on strip mining consumers' data or governments that depend on censoring public opinion. We can use the

global power of open source and enforced compliance within our borders to ensure that EU companies can concentrate on improving our digital servants' talents and skills, in our homes, workplaces and places of leisure, in agriculture and the great outdoors, as well as in the public spaces in between.

Only without vendor lock-in, using open standards, proven interoperability and open source assets, can devices and servants be operated at an ecological optimum and sustained over the lifetime of a consumer. If we can ensure that at least within the borders of our laws we can interact with our digital servants under legal privileges similar to those we enjoy with our spouses, only the technical challenges of seamless interaction or digital augmentation remain to be solved; and those are significant enough.

The battle for attention and addiction

Facebook, Google and in fact every form of wooing or advertisement, is about influencing our prejudices in favour of their sponsors. A front-door salesman would grow hungry, hoarse or just tired

after meeting a few potential customers a day. Yet cloud servers can whisper into millions of minds at once, have infinite patience and perseverance, no conscience for lack of conscious and, with the help of deep analysis of clicks, likes and purchases of social peers, evolve content into the very gestalt consumers like best, often past the threshold of addiction, creating a feedback bubble that is difficult to escape.

Within these automatically individualized bubbles self-reinforcement leads to radicalization of opinion and expression that can easily lead to monstrous content. And the social media CEOs who merely intended 'to connect people' [2], suddenly find themselves accused for the damage that creates while the effort for clearing out data along a diversity of guidelines that matches their user base, threatens their bottom line.

Intended or not by the providers, the evolution of social media and streaming video will seek to keep the exclusive attention of a consumer, because it's much more expensive to gain back from someone who strayed elsewhere. With the help of decades of cognitive science and the

almost limitless economy of scale that software provides, endless scrolls of auto-start content are generated and carefully self-tune to a victim's preference, a permanent cliffhanger, aimed to wring peak purchasing budget and attention from consumers.

As they scale to billions of clients, their gravitational influencing pull eclipses that of major nations, upsetting their leaders, who with a focus on ground and borders, didn't realize clouds could do that.

The serious game of making rules or sovereignty in a digitalized society

Little is so important for the evolution of higher life forms as playing: you can observe it with the small kitten of the big cats or your own kids who have evolved to take it dead seriously. Where playful games may mostly hone individual behaviour for the big cats beyond instinct, with herd animals like humans it evolved into social

code, which some have lifted to the level of Gods, others turned into legislation: the main difference between games, ideology, laws or religion isn't as much in the code, as in the scale of its application... which of course depends on the quality of that code. Some games are so successful that they become serious enough to write down their rules. And increasingly we have computers execute them.

Computers started as a faster replacement for mechanical calculators operating on minimally contentious numbers while the first nodes of the internet connected nerds interested in little more than technology. Without measurable impact on society, there was no need for regulation. Today 'Very Personal Computers' and the internet are moving past the inflection point where the majority of all human created content and interaction is not just passing through them, but actively enabled, blocked, rein-

forced or transformed by code and AI models applying bias, rules and regulation across every hop, from edge to core and back into our brains.

What started as a playfully nerdy version of a college yearbook (Facebook), a better way to rank the relevance of Internet pages (Google), a more convenient way to sell music on a mobile player (iPhone), or an attempt to reduce IT hardware spends off season (Amazon Cloud) has become political, simply because their code is now applied at planet scale throughout the Internet, with little regard to existing borders and regulations. China was one of the first major nations to erect internet border controls against content but, as the digitalization of societies progresses, the code at the core becomes political—even for individuals—because of its vast scope and scale of application.

Politicians are 'influencers' by default and are ever more interested in controlling digital platforms within what they consider their domain. As US web giants search for growth planet wide and functionally ever deeper, this increases the attack surface, while political leaders outside the United States reduce their tolerance to US companies exerting influence, even if those never wanted the political ballast: "just connecting people" becomes political aggression when you turn more minds than an opponent.

And because the direction and impact of digitalization is clearly before us, regulation needs to switch from reactive to proactive and start to plan with a desired target state, best inferred from what already exists outside the digital domain.

To continue demanding that cyberspace and the clouds have a distinct set of rules [3], values or morals from the physical world on the ground is, at best, foolish. It is more likely just intended to protect vested interests; ground staked during the early Wild West of the internet.

Any sovereign nation, and in fact every smaller social aggregate with its own rules, only has two choices going forward: regulate any code that reaches a scale or scope big enough to change society, or lose sovereignty to that code.

When an operating system like Android or a browser like Chrome is used by practically everyone for practically every digital interaction, or an Office suite like Microsoft's handles the vast majority of all structured documents in current use, billions of users send and receive trillions of messages a week with a single app, changing a single line of code becomes political, a developer SCRUM meeting a session of parliament, an application redesign a change of constitution.

The separation of powers and the delegation of legislative and executive functions to choice or chosen individuals built societies and gave birth to nations. In the case of code that has amassed enough traction to change society, or by chance becomes the sole player at a social inflection point, it is

no longer just an issue of lacking competition: it risks violating sovereignty. Such code needs to be taken from the very hands and corporations that created it, its fate no longer determined by the CEO but the sovereign, in every form of government.

Global information technology in a divided planet

While technology seems less political than content does, the current trade wars end a rather free global flow of technological ideas and products seen during recent decades. As China is challenging Western digital industry leadership, the United States has resorted to blocking its manufacturing supplies to protect markets it considers its own. Where previously the IT industry was consolidating towards one global player for each of the many puzzle pieces required to build chips and systems, suddenly nobody is left with the ability to produce or maintain the full stack, without at least some ingredients from beyond the trenches that sprung up everywhere.

All of these technology assets, whether they are used for physical manufacturing or digital replication, could be redeveloped within each block, given enough time and budget. But they would initially be inferior in quality and price, and not competitive once a barrier was lifted again. China has made it national policy to develop such a full stack; outside the United States, nobody else currently wants to make that sacrifice.

Whilst an ideal solution might be to give each nation on Earth a critical piece of the IT stack and thus assure global cooperation, criticality changes over time and, in any case, the biggest players have their sights set on dominance.

Europe, and whoever else currently holds a critical piece, needs to guard and aim to expand their assets judiciously in order to retain a minority vote and influence in this struggle by allying with other significant economic blocks. At the same time, Europe must modularize its technology and supply chains to minimize impact as barriers shift and change. All players still need consumers to feed their economies, even if the growth potential of the Chinese

domestic market alone is bigger than that of any other newly isolated block.

Open source is a great tool to level an uneven playing field and much easier to move and copy than silicon foundries. But like everything else invented or picked up by humankind, it's also turned into a weapon. More and more it is used to level the competitor's garden into a barren wasteland without any revenue to sustain him.

A weapon's preferred use is actually negotiation and that is what Europe must do, understanding that things can only get more difficult if our economy and thus the strength of our arguments get left behind. This pandemic, the next, climate change and pollution will eventually have everyone against a wall, with only two options: successful negotiation or mutual suffering.

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